

The Role of Genetic Mutations in CTNNB1 and APC Genes on the Craniopharyngioma

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Abstract

Craniopharyngioma occurs in about 0.5 to 2 per million people each year and has a bimodal distribution, 5 to 14 years and 50 to 74 years. Many experts consider craniopharyngioma to be a chronic disease because it tends to recur even when completely surgically removed. The tumor itself is usually not dangerous, as it is benign and rarely becomes malignant. However, the location of the tumor is such that it can compress the pituitary gland, leading to hormonal dysfunction. There are two types of craniopharyngiomas: adamantomatous and papillary. The former occurs more commonly in children, while the latter is more common in adults. Adamantomatous craniopharyngiomas arise from cells in an embryonic structure called the craniopharyngeal canal. They can be solid or form a hollow (cystic) structure filled with a dark brown to black fluid (similar to motor oil) and are often calcified. Papillary craniopharyngiomas are rarer and arise from cells in the anterior pituitary gland. They are usually well-circumscribed and can also be solid or cystic, although they are filled with a yellow, viscous fluid. Craniopharyngioma is caused by abnormalities of embryonic tissue in the sellar and parasellar regions. Adamantomatous craniopharyngioma, which occurs more frequently in children, and papillary craniopharyngioma, which occurs more frequently in adults, have different embryonic origins.

Keywords: Craniopharyngioma, Tumor (neoplasm), Sell Turcica, Genetic Mutation.

Craniopharyngioma Overview

A craniopharyngioma is a benign tumor (neoplasm) that arises from embryonic tissue in and around the sella region (parasellar region). The sella region is located in the center of the base of the skull and specifically contains the pituitary gland, the "master gland" of the body, and the sella turcica, the bony depression in the skull (specifically in the sphenoid bone) where the pituitary gland sits.1

Craniopharyngioma occurs in about 0.5 to 2 per million people each year and has a bimodal distribution, 5 to 14 years and 50 to 74 years. Many experts consider craniopharyngioma to be a chronic disease because it tends to

recur even when completely surgically removed. The tumor itself is usually not dangerous, as it is benign and rarely becomes malignant. However, the location of the tumor is such that it can compress the pituitary gland, leading to hormonal dysfunction. The optic chiasm, where the two optic nerves partially cross, is located above the pituitary gland and can therefore be compressed by the craniopharyngioma, leading to visual impairment. The hypothalamus, to which the pituitary gland is attached, can also be damaged, especially after surgery.

Because the hypothalamus regulates many biological functions, damage to this structure is associated with symptoms such as obesity (hypothalamic obesity) and sleep-wake cycle disruption. Another anatomical structure that can be compressed by a craniopharyngioma is the foramen of Monro within the ventricles. If this foramen becomes blocked, cerebrospinal fluid that normally circulates in the brain and spinal cord can build up (a condition known as hydrocephalus), potentially leading to a variety of symptoms, including an enlarged head in infants. Headaches and nausea may also occur due to increased intracranial pressure. Treatment for craniopharyngioma includes surgical removal of the tumor and radiation therapy, especially when the tumor cannot be completely removed due to its location. Depending on the patient's needs, specific hormone therapy may also be required.¹

Figure 1: Schematic of the craniopharyngioma in the human brain.¹

There are two types of craniopharyngiomas: adamantinomatous and papillary. The former occurs more commonly in children, while the latter is more common in adults. Adamantinomatous craniopharyngiomas arise from cells in an embryonic structure called the craniopharyngeal canal. They can be solid or form a hollow (cystic) structure filled with a dark brown to black fluid (similar to motor oil) and are often calcified. Papillary craniopharyngiomas are rarer and arise from cells in the anterior pituitary gland. They are usually well-circumscribed and can also be solid or cystic, although they are filled with a yellow, viscous fluid. They rarely calcify. The clinical presentation of both types of craniopharyngiomas

is largely similar. Because craniopharyngiomas are rare tumors with atypical and nonspecific symptoms, they can be diagnosed many years after symptoms appear. Early diagnosis is beneficial because it can greatly improve the quality of life of affected individuals and reduce the risk of long-term complications.¹

Clinical Signs and Symptoms of Craniopharyngiomas

They are almost always benign but can cause symptoms by compressing nearby important anatomical structures such as the pituitary gland, hypothalamus, and the junction of the two optic nerves (optic chiasm). Limb weakness (paresis), difficulty walking, seizures, and psychiatric symptoms such as paranoid delusions can also occur from brain compression. Another common consequence of tumor compression is increased intracranial pressure, which can cause symptoms such as headaches and nausea. Because craniopharyngiomas are difficult to treat and are in a difficult anatomical location to access and close to many important structures, patients can experience many symptoms that are related to the treatment of the disease rather than the disease itself.^{1,2}

Figure 2: Radiological images of craniopharyngioma and adamantinomatosis in the brain.¹

Pituitary gland dysfunction: The pituitary gland is the body's "master gland" and its integrity is critical to many hormonal processes throughout the body. Most patients with craniopharyngioma experience hormonal (endocrine) deficiencies due to the tumor compressing the pituitary gland. Deficiencies can affect any hormonal pathway controlled by the pituitary gland and are more pronounced in adult craniopharyngioma patients. GH (growth hormone) deficiency can lead to reduced growth rates in children.

Delayed puberty and absence of menstruation in women (amenorrhea) can occur in cases of FSH and LH (gonadotropin) deficiency. Craniopharyngioma can also commonly cause precocious puberty. ACTH (adrenocorticotrophic hormone) deficiency can cause many symptoms, such as weakness and fatigue. TSH (thyroid stimulating hormone) deficiency is associated with many clinical manifestations, including fatigue, general weakness, menstrual irregularities, and forgetfulness. Pituitary gland compression can also be the cause of a disorder called central diabetes insipidus (not related to the more common diabetes, also known as diabetes mellitus), which is characterized by excessive thirst (polydipsia), excessive urination (polyuria), and excessive thirst (polydipsia).^{1,2}

Figure 3: Radiological image of a craniopharyngioma tumor in the brain.¹

Hypothalamic dysfunction: The hypothalamus is connected to the pituitary gland and controls its hormone secretion, in addition to being responsible for regulating numerous biological processes. Hypothalamic dysfunction can occur due to compression of the hypothalamus by a tumor, but it can also occur as a result of surgical removal of the tumor (resection). One of the main symptoms associated with hypothalamic dysfunction is hypothalamic obesity, a type of obesity that occurs even with calorie restriction and lifestyle changes. Froelich syndrome is a combination of hypothalamic obesity, delayed sexual development, and small testicles caused by damage to the hypothalamus. Other symptoms of hypothalamic dysfunction include changes in behavior and imbalances in body temperature, thirst, heart rate, and blood pressure. Hypothalamic dysfunction can also lead to sleep-wake cycle disorders, such as non-24-hour sleep-wake syndrome. Symptoms of this disorder include insomnia at night and excessive sleepiness during the day.^{1,3}

Figure 4: Other radiological images of craniopharyngioma tumor and adamantinomatosis.¹

Optic Nerves and Optic Chiasm Compression: The optic nerves, which carry visual information to the brain, pass partly above the pituitary gland, forming a structure called the optic chiasm. Both the optic nerves and the optic chiasm can be compressed by the craniopharyngioma. This can lead to two main visual symptoms: blurred vision (reduced visual acuity) and loss of vision in certain areas of the visual field (visual field defects). Visual symptoms are common in people with craniopharyngioma.

Obstructed Foramen of Monro: The brain contains the ventricular system: a system of four cavities (ventricles) in which cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) is produced and circulates. The craniopharyngioma may block some of the channels that connect the ventricles to each other (foramen of Monro). If the foramen of Monro becomes blocked, cerebrospinal fluid cannot circulate properly and accumulates (hydrocephalus). Symptoms associated with hydrocephalus are numerous and depend on the age of the affected person. Infants may be malnourished, irritable, and have an enlarged head. Children and adults may have symptoms such as neck pain, headache, vomiting, and blurred vision.^{1,4}

Figure 5: Radiological images of craniopharyngioma tumor associated with other brain disorders. Treatment-related (iatrogenic) complications: Craniopharyngiomas are difficult to remove surgically because they are usually located near several anatomical structures that may be damaged during surgery. Craniopharyngiomas also tend to recur, even when they appear to have been completely removed. Therefore, many patients have to undergo multiple surgeries during their lifetime. The consequences of surgery include damage to nearby anatomical structures, especially the pituitary gland and hypothalamus. Deficits in cognition, memory, and attention can also be consequences of surgery. Radiation therapy is usually given after surgery, especially in patients in whom the tumor cannot be completely removed. The internal carotid arteries can be damaged by such treatment (radiation-induced vasculopathies), leading to cerebrovascular complications such as dilation and weakening of the blood vessel wall (aneurysm) and Moyamoya disease, in which the internal carotid arteries narrow, which can lead to further complications such as headaches, strokes, and seizures. Radiation exposure is also a risk factor for the development of brain tumors such as gliomas.^{1,4.}

Figure 6: 3D images of a craniopharyngioma tumor in the brain.

Long-term outcomes: When managed properly, people with craniopharyngioma have a greater than 90 percent survival rate beyond 20 years. Many experts consider craniopharyngioma to be a chronic disease because the rate of tumor recurrence is high even with apparent complete removal of the tumor. Important complications that can lead to death include: stroke, cardiac complications, respiratory complications, chronic hypothalamic insufficiency, hormonal deficiencies, and seizures. In very rare cases, craniopharyngioma can become malignant (transform into a malignant tumor).^{1,5}

Figure 7: Bar chart of patients with adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma (ACP) and papillary craniopharyngioma (PCP) by density and age coefficient.

Etiology of Craniopharyngioma

Craniopharyngioma is caused by abnormalities of embryonic tissue in the sellar and parasellar regions. Adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma, which occurs more frequently in children, and papillary craniopharyngioma, which occurs more frequently in adults, have different embryonic origins. Adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma: Adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma arises from the transformation into tumor cells (neoplastic transformation) of cells from the craniopharyngioma canal, a fetal structure connected to Rathke's pouch, which gives rise to part of the pituitary gland. The exact cause of adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma is unknown, although mutations in the CTNNB1 gene, located on the short arm of chromosome 3 at 3p22.1, or the APC gene, located on the long arm of chromosome 5 at 5q22.2, are present in more than 70% of tumors. These genes produce a protein called beta-catenin, which is important in fetal development (embryogenesis).

Therefore, mutations in these genes may play a role in the development of adamantomatous craniopharyngioma.^{1,6}

Figure 8: Schematic of the structure of the CTNNB1 gene.¹

Papillary craniopharyngioma: Papillary craniopharyngioma is caused by a change in the cell type (metaplasia) of cells in the anterior pituitary gland. This results in the formation of nests made of a type of cell called squamous cells. In the case of adamantomatous craniopharyngioma, the exact cause of papillary craniopharyngioma is unknown.^{1,6}

Figure 9: Schematic of the structure of the APC gene.

Craniopharyngioma

Craniopharyngioma occurs in about 0.5 to 2 per million people per year and accounts for about 1.2 to 4% of all

intracranial tumors in children. They develop most frequently in two age groups (bimodal incidence): children 0 to 14 years and adults 50 to 74 years. They occur equally in men and women. Adamantomatous craniopharyngioma is the most common, accounting for 86 to 89% of all craniopharyngiomas.^{1,7}

Craniopharyngioma-Related Disorders

Disorders that can damage or compress structures close to the sellar region, such as the pituitary gland, hypothalamus, and optic chiasm, can have clinical manifestations similar to craniopharyngioma. Examples of entities that can cause compression or damage include tumors, cysts, and blood vessel disorders.^{1,8}

Pituitary adenomas are hormone-secreting tumors of the pituitary gland. They can secrete different pituitary hormones, depending on the type of cell affected. This can lead to various clinical manifestations associated with the excess hormone secretion. For example, a prolactinoma is a pituitary adenoma that secretes prolactin. Symptoms related to excess prolactin include irregular menstrual periods, infertility, milk production even if the affected woman is not pregnant, and erectile dysfunction in men. As is the case with craniopharyngioma, pituitary adenomas can also cause compression of the pituitary gland, leading to pituitary hormone deficiency, and compression of the optic nerves and optic chiasm, leading to visual impairment. Some pituitary adenomas, known as non-functioning adenomas, do not secrete any pituitary hormones, but can still be responsible for pressure symptoms.^{1,8}

Figure 10: Schematic of the molecular mechanism of the APC gene in the cytoplasm.

Glioma is a tumor of the central nervous system that arises from glial cells, a type of cell widely found in the nervous system. Gliomas occur most often in the brain and rarely in the spinal cord. They occur at different ages, depending on the subtype. As they develop, gliomas can compress the areas of the brain in which they occur and cause a variety of symptoms, including headache, nausea, vomiting, cognitive impairment, seizures, gait imbalance, language impairment (aphasia), weakness on one side of the body (hemiparesis), visual field defects, and personality changes. Structures compressed by gliomas, such as the pituitary gland, hypothalamus, and optic chiasm, can have symptoms similar to those of craniopharyngioma.^{1,8}

As their name suggests, intracranial germ cell tumors are derived from germ cells and are located inside the skull. The exact mechanism of intracranial germ cell tumors is not known, but embryonic abnormalities play a role. They can clinically mimic craniopharyngiomas by compressing structures such as the pituitary gland, hypothalamus, and optic chiasm. Langerhans cell histiocytosis (LCH) is a rare disease that involves the proliferation of Langerhans cells, which are derived from the bone marrow. Symptoms involving multiple organ systems can result, including hormonal abnormalities such as diabetes insipidus. If the anterior pituitary gland is affected by LCH, the patient may have low levels of pituitary hormones.^{1,8}

An aneurysm is a localized weakening and bulging of a blood vessel. A cerebral aneurysm can bleed and rupture, leading to subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH) and symptoms such as headache, seizures, and loss of consciousness. The outward bulging of the vessel can also compress nearby anatomical structures. If the aneurysm is located near the pituitary gland or optic nerve, visual symptoms and hormonal deficiencies may occur. As with tumors and aneurysms, cysts of multiple origins can compress anatomical structures near the sellar region, leading to symptoms similar to craniopharyngioma. This is especially true for Rathke's cleft cysts, arachnoid cysts, and colloid cysts of the third ventricle. Diagnosis of craniopharyngioma.^{1,8}

Diagnosis of Craniopharyngioma

Diagnosis of craniopharyngioma is based on three main methods: clinical history and physical examination, laboratory tests, and imaging.

Clinical history and physical examination: The diagnosis of craniopharyngioma requires an extensive clinical his-

tory and physical examination. Clinical manifestations that are suspicious for craniopharyngioma include a combination of headache, visual impairment, growth retardation, increased thirst and urination (polydipsia and polyuria), and other signs of hormonal (endocrine) deficiency.

Laboratory tests: Laboratory tests are usually needed to confirm the clinical suspicion of endocrine deficiency. Typically, craniopharyngioma tests include evaluation of serum electrolytes as well as all hormones that can be affected by pituitary dysfunction: GH, IGF-1, TSH, free thyroxine, cortisol, FSH, LH, testosterone, estradiol, and prolactin. Imaging: Computed tomography (CT scan) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are the imaging modalities of choice for diagnosing craniopharyngioma. CT scan is used to detect tumor calcification, while MRI can be used to detect fluid accumulation within cystic tumors.^{1,9}

Craniopharyngioma Treatment Pathways

People with craniopharyngioma may initially present with neurological, visual, and hormonal abnormalities and may require evaluation by neurologists, ophthalmologists, and endocrinologists. A radiologist or neurologist is then needed to interpret the medical imaging. A combination of clinical presentation, laboratory values, and medical imaging will lead to a clinical diagnosis of craniopharyngioma. The diagnosis can be confirmed by a neuropathologist who analyzes the tumor microscopically after removal (resection).^{1,10}

Figure 11: Schematic of the surgical procedure for removal of a craniopharyngioma tumor

Neurosurgical treatment plays a key role in the management of craniopharyngioma. If there is no risk of damage to adjacent anatomical structures, the neurosurgeon will remove the entire tumor. If the tumor is adjacent to vital structures, the surgical team may decide not to remove the entire tumor. Radiation oncologists will then be involved to administer radiotherapy to the patient. There is no clear agreement on the balance that should be struck between attempting to remove the tumor and radiotherapy. Multiple surgical procedures may be required over the course of a patient's life, as craniopharyngioma recurs even when it appears to have been completely removed.^{1,11}

Figure 12: Schematic of the normal and mutant nucleotide sequences of the APC gene.

Endocrinologists are often involved, as hormone replacement therapy is required to treat patients with hypothalamic and pituitary gland dysfunction. Hypothalamic obesity is also an issue that can affect the quality of life of affected individuals. Medications such as Octreotide, which reduces insulin secretion, and bariatric surgery may be indicated for some morbidly obese patients. Given the high recurrence rate of craniopharyngioma and the multiple effects it can have on the body, affected individuals usually need to be monitored by multiple medical specialists throughout their lives.^{1,11}

Figure 13: Schematic of the biochemical mechanism of wild-type and mutant APC and CTNNB1 genes.

Discussion

They are almost always benign but can cause symptoms by compressing nearby important anatomical structures such as the pituitary gland, hypothalamus, and the junction of the two optic nerves (optic chiasm). Limb weakness (paresis), difficulty walking, seizures, and psychiatric symptoms such as paranoid delusions can also occur from brain compression. Another common consequence of tumor compression is increased intracranial pressure, which can cause symptoms such as headaches and nausea.

Because craniopharyngiomas are difficult to treat and are in a difficult anatomical location to access and close to many important structures, patients can experience many symptoms that are related to the treatment of the disease rather than the disease itself. Craniopharyngioma is caused by abnormalities of embryonic tissue in the sellar and parasellar regions. Adamantomatous craniopharyngioma, which occurs more frequently in children, and papillary craniopharyngioma, which occurs more frequently in adults, have different embryonic origins. Adamantomatous craniopharyngioma: Adamantomatous craniopharyngioma arises from the transformation into tumor cells (neoplastic transformation) of cells from the craniopharyngioma canal, a fetal structure connected to Rathke's pouch, which gives rise to part of the pituitary gland. The exact cause of adamantomatous craniopharyngioma is unknown, although mutations in the CTNNB1 gene, located on the short arm of chromosome 3 at 3p22.1, or the APC gene, located on the long arm of chromosome 5 at 5q22.2, are present in more than 70% of tumors. These genes produce a protein called beta-catenin, which is important in fetal development (embryogenesis). Therefore, mutations in these genes may play a role in the development of adamantomatous craniopharyngioma. Diagnosis of craniopharyngioma is based on three main methods: clinical history and physical examination, laboratory tests, and imaging.

Clinical history and physical examination: The diagnosis of craniopharyngioma requires an extensive clinical history and physical examination. Clinical manifestations that are suspicious for craniopharyngioma include a combination of headache, visual impairment, growth retardation, increased thirst and urination (polydipsia and polyuria), and other signs of hormonal (endocrine) deficiency. People with craniopharyngioma may initially present with neurological, visual, and hormonal abnormalities and may require evaluation by neurologists, ophthalmologists, and endocrinologists. A radiologist or neurologist is then needed to interpret the medical imaging. Neurosurgical treatment plays a key role in the management of craniopharyngioma. If there is no risk of damage to adjacent anatomical structures, the neurosurgeon will remove the entire tumor. If the tumor is adjacent to vital structures, the surgical team may decide not to remove the entire tumor. Radiation oncologists will then be involved to administer radiotherapy to the patient. There is no clear agreement on the balance that should be struck between attempting to remove the tumor and radiotherapy. Multiple surgical procedures may be required over the course of a patient's life, as craniopharyngioma recurs

even when it appears to have been completely removed. 1-11.

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